

Rule for Thee but Not for Me: From Roberts to Vinson, a Statistical Analysis of the Role of Religion in the Supreme Court

Cambridge Journal of Political
Affairs
Volume 6, Issue 1 (2025): 178-199
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DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.16632509
cambridgepoliticalaffairs.co.uk

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In recent years, the Supreme Court has increasingly taken up cases involving religious freedom, reflecting growing societal and legal tensions surrounding the role of religion in public life. The Roberts Court, for instance, has ruled in favour of religious organisations far more frequently than its predecessors (approximately 81% of the time compared to approximately 50% before) and has been the centre of several high-profile rulings in favour of mainstream Christian organisations. The purpose of this study is to determine whether the legal facts align with public perception—or more pointedly, prove whether or not there truly exists a statistically significant “religious preference” on the Court (and towards whom). In this paper, I examine the outcomes of First Amendment religious cases in the Supreme Court over the past 80 years, focusing on a statistical analysis of case outcomes and justices' voting patterns. The study evaluates the success rates of the parties involved and the effective impacts of decisions relative to the broader Christian mainstream to discern the true nature of these cases over time. Notably, I identify a shift under the Roberts Court, characterised by a unique level of religious fervour in its rulings. Through quantitative analysis of judicial decisions and voting records, this research highlights trends in case outcomes and their implications for religious freedoms and establishment clause interpretations.

INTRODUCTION

The 1960s in America were a crucible of ideological contention. Throughout a decade marked by a vigorous tug-of-war between progressive activists and a conservative tradition, the Supreme Court rose to the forefront. As the nation grappled with civil rights, sexual revolution, and the Vietnam War, the Supreme Court, under Chief Justice Earl Warren, became an assertive player at the heart of the most contentious issues of the time. Landmark rulings such as *Miranda v. Arizona* (1966) and *Loving v. Virginia* (1967) enshrined the 60s as the period of judicial activism, morphing the bench into the pivotal battleground where the ethos of American society was being defined, tested, and transformed. It was a time when the judiciary not only reflected but also shaped the zeitgeist, carving out a more pronounced role for itself amid the nation's ideological struggles. As a result, it is no wonder why political scientist and legal scholar Bruce Schulman refers to this period as “one of the most consequential periods for civil and political rights in American history” (Schulman, 2008). That being said, for as attention-grabbing and hotly debated as cases surrounding segregation or due process may be, it can be argued that no issues have more fundamentally defined the way our legal system works or shaped our opinion on the legitimacy of the very “referees of the game” than that of religious liberty & the separation of church and state (Schulman, 2008).

As opposed to conventional ideas of civil rights and protections that developed as America matured, religious liberties are one of the few issues baked into the American identity from the start (Hobb, 1902). The history of the Church, and in a much broader sense, religion as a whole, in America since the beginning, marked a sharp contrast with most of the religious and ecclesiastical practices across the pond in Europe. As legal scholar Sanford Hobb notes, “Its resultant principle of Liberty on which religious institutions and life in the United States are founded today, was a uniquely American in design” (Hobb, 1902) This principle, cutting right across that which the Old World had for all the Christian centuries regarded as axiomatic, illustrates, better than all else, the profound idea that “American law was the growth of necessity, not the wisdom of individuals. It was not an acquisition from abroad; it was begotten

from the American mind, of which it was a natural and inevitable, but also a slow and gradual development” (Hobb, 1902). After all, Thomas Jefferson famously declared his job in creating the constitution was to build “a wall of separation between Church and State” (Cook, 2014).

In her book *First Amendment Religious Liberties: Supreme Court Decisions and Public Opinion, 1947-2013*, political scientist and legal scholar Tracey Cook claimed that over the last approximately forty years, sizeable majorities of Americans have reported support for the general principle of the “separation of church and state” (Cook, 2014). At the same time, according to a study conducted by the PEW Research Center, about one-third of Americans (35%) now see the high Court as friendly toward religion, nearly double the share that said this in a Center survey conducted in March and April of 2019 (18%) (Tevington, 2022). This increase follows a 2021-22 Supreme Court term that produced several decisions with implications for religion: the *Dobbs v. Jackson Women’s Health Organisation* case that ended the constitutional right to abortion; *Kennedy v. Bremerton School District* which ruled that favoured a high school football coach who led Christian prayers after games; and *Carson v. Makin*, a ruling that allowed public funding for private religious schools (Tevington, 2022). Compounding the concern, only 25 percent of Americans report “quite a lot” or “a great deal” of confidence in the Court (Maroni, 2022).

The significance of these trends is simple: judicial opinions do not occur in a vacuum. Pre-existing attitudes toward the Court shape how individuals respond to each ruling. Thus, the problem of the Supreme Court is that it is a generally *disliked* institution heavily dependent upon its long-term *likeability* (or, in more technical terms, legitimacy) for its efficacy and survival (Gibson and Nelson, 2014). The ongoing perception of the Supreme Court as being “pro-religion” (or at least somewhat softer on religion today than in the past) coupled with a decline in public trust, poses significant risks to the fabric of American democracy and the principle of judicial impartiality. As a result, this perception can erode the Court’s role as a neutral arbiter, essential for maintaining a balanced and inclusive legal system. Thus, in the face of such a crisis, the natural question turns to whether the *feeling* of religious preference by the Court in the past (and present) matches the *facts* shown in their actual outcomes. The goal of this paper is to empirically determine whether religious preferences can be quantitatively demonstrated within judicial decision-making in First Amendment religious freedom cases.¹ Or more precisely, to what extent, if any, does religious preference exist on the Supreme Court?

By exploring the extent to which judges’ religious affiliations and case demographics influence their rulings, I aim to uncover the underlying factors that shape judicial behaviour in these contentious cases. To investigate whether the Supreme Court’s decisions on First Amendment religious freedom cases are influenced by external factors, I employ a quantitative analysis on more than 100 First Amendment religious liberty Court rulings dating as far back as 1945. The dataset includes a wide range of variables, such as case outcome, case popularity, the type of claimant, and other socio-political factors that might impact the result. This data-driven approach allows for a comprehensive examination of the influences on Supreme Court religious-freedom decisions. The findings are crucial because they challenge the ideal of judicial independence and impartiality. By demonstrating that external factors play a significant role in judicial decision-making, the study highlights the complexities and potential vulnerabilities in the legal adjudication process of religious freedom cases. Furthermore, the findings substantiate the hypothesis that judicial decisions, particularly those concerning First Amendment religious liberties, are not made in a vacuum but in fact are affected by a broader religious and political context.

Now, before going any further, there are a few claims and issues surrounding analyses of cases of religious liberties that should be pre-empted and are essential to understanding what this article is trying to achieve. The first is the (mistaken) idea that the public perception of the Supreme Court’s behaviour (that is, a supposed “legal crisis of religion”) can only be validated if the court were actively taking up more cases (Hall, 2009). It is the idea that if the court honestly had an agenda, it would seek out more cases in *scale*. If that was not the case, then any such view of favouritism or partisan behaviour would merely be due to one’s political biases. This is a bit of a far-fetched argument, but a convincing one at first glance. As shown in Figure 0, a simple layman’s analysis of the Washington University of St. Louis Supreme Court

¹ A “religious freedom” case is a legal dispute that involves the interpretation and application of laws protecting individuals’ or organisations’ rights to practice, express, or be free from religion, often under the First Amendment or related statutes.

database for all 113 First Amendment cases since 1945 filtered for religion (establishment clause², free exercise³, and parochial school cases) shows why the devil’s advocate’s argument is so compelling (Washington University Database, 2024). At face value, one would expect a so-called “hockey stick” graph where, say, in the last 20 years, there had been a sudden rise in the number of cases the court had taken or even a change in perceived outcome. After all, even when filtered for conservative and liberal decisions, they remain (relatively) split, implying that this must simply be the frustration of the uneducated voter (Hall, 2009):

Figure o. Supreme Court Religious Liberty Cases by Outcome (1945-2022). Note: This chart was generated on the Washington University of St. Louis’ Supreme Court Database. The x-axis represents the count of cases while the y-axis represents the year. Additionally, red represents a conservative decision while blue a liberal one as defined by the database.

This argument is misleading for two reasons. First, it fails to recognise the Court as a *finite* institution. While Congress comprises hundreds of people and tens of thousands of legislative aides, the Court (in practice) is just nine people. Nine people have to hear every case, question every oral argument, and write opinions on matters of national consequence. In fact, the Court is only able to accept around 100-150 of the more than 7,000 cases that it is asked to review each year (uscourts.gov). Just because there aren’t, say, 10 times more cases on religious liberties being heard in 2022 than in 1979 does not mean that the

² An “Establishment Clause” case is a legal dispute concerning whether a government action or law improperly endorses, supports, or favours a particular religion or religion in general, violating the First Amendment’s prohibition on government establishment of religion.

³ A “Free Exercise Clause” case is a legal dispute that addresses whether a law or government action improperly restricts an individual’s or group’s right to practice their religion, as protected under the First Amendment.

situation is the same. At the same time, the Court has slowed in the number of cases heard *overall* per term, not just fewer First Amendment Religious cases alone, disposing of just a meagre 15 cases before June 2022 compared to 157 by the same time in 1923 (Hurley, 2023). Thus, even if there were fewer First Amendment cases taken in scale, it is more likely due to a larger trend of the Court as a whole rather than something specific to religious cases (Hurley, 2023). That leads to the second reason, that such a blanket analysis, while considering *scale*, woefully neglects *significance* (Hall, 2009). While it is true that case outcomes have been relatively constant and evenly divided, the more critical questions are who is winning their cases and, more importantly, why. As will be explored throughout this work, the strawman's argument fails to consider the *nature* of the cases. What type of party brought it? Was it striking down a law? Did these cases match public opinion? Have more extreme measures been taken recently, even if the number of cases has remained the same? These are all questions left by the wayside when resorting to the armchair analysis offered by our "enlightened" strawman.

The second issue is that in the realm of political science scholarship, the analysis of Supreme Court cases concerning religious liberties has predominantly been qualitative, with scholar Mark David Hall noting, "Although broad claims are often made about these [religious liberty] cases, they are either unsupported generalities or extrapolations" (Hall, 2009). For Hall and many others within the field, there is a growing feeling that much of the current work aligns more closely with that of legal scholarship and often focuses on anecdotal, high-profile decisions rather than on the trends and data behind them (Hall, 2009). While this analysis certainly has its merits, it is contrasted with the work of some of the leaders in the field like Lee Epstein, William M. Landes, and Richard A. Posner who focus their research on Supreme Court decisions in the business sector and often employ a more quantitative methodology, utilising statistical models and quantitative data to assess patterns and impacts within rulings (Epstein, 2017). This divergence reflects a tendency to approach religious liberty cases as unique, complex, and deeply embedded in historical and cultural contexts, requiring a nuanced, case-by-case analysis. While there is undoubtedly merit to tying the cultural and contextual with the legal, the quantitative has seldom been represented in matters concerning religious liberties (Cook, 2014). For this reason, my aim in this article is to meticulously dissect the current crisis of religious liberties in America in a way that has not been done before. With longstanding societal perceptions and the apparent crisis squarely established (along with an understanding of present academic shortcomings), this work seeks to identify the *fact* within the *feeling*.

LITERATURE REVIEW:

The study of religion's role in court cases represents a rich and multifaceted field that intersects with numerous dimensions of law, society, and individual belief systems. As judicial decisions are influenced not only by the letter of the law but also by the personal convictions of those who interpret it, the role of religion emerges as a particularly compelling area of inquiry. This complexity is deepened by the diverse ways religious beliefs can manifest within legal arguments, from influencing judges' interpretations of statutes to shaping the moral and ethical frameworks within legal debates. Moreover, the varying degrees of religious influence across different legal systems and cultural contexts offer a broad spectrum for analysis, making the study of religion's salience in court cases rich and crucial for understanding the wider implications of jurisprudence in contemporary society. In other words, analysis of religion and the law (even empirical) in certain respects is nothing new, and there are, in particular, three significant areas of study about First Amendment religious cases and the Court that are worth beginning with.

The first and most obvious types of studies focus on the straight-up outcome of these cases. One such empirical study, conducted by Gregory C. Sisk, Michael Heise, and Andrew P. Morriss (more colloquially referred to as the Sisk study), examined the resolution of religious freedom issues, including free exercise and establishment clause cases in the lower federal courts (both district courts and the Courts of Appeals) from 1986 through 1995. When they finally were able to publish in 2004, they concluded that "In our study of religious freedom decisions, the single most prominent, salient, and consistent influence on judicial decision-making was religion in terms of affiliation of the claimant, the background of the judge, and the demographics of the community" (Sisk et al., 2005). Put simply, while it should be noted that the Sisk study sought future confirmation of their findings, at a base level they suggested that "religious factors are meaningfully associated with judging outcomes" (Sisk et al., 2004).

Another area of interest lies away from case *outcomes* and with case *claimants*. Regarding the claimants specifically, their position in the religious mainstream holds some weight and has in the past yielded mixed results. Sisk et al. (2004) found that "Muslims, far outside the American mainstream, may be

significantly disadvantaged in asserting Free Exercise & Accommodation claims.” In a 1999 empirical study of free exercise decisions in the United States Courts of Appeals, James Brent found that mainstream Catholics and Protestants were *more* likely than non-mainstream claimants to win free exercise claims (Brent, 1999). However, these studies were thrown into tension with a 1993 article from Joseph A. Ignagni, who examined United States Supreme Court free exercise decisions from 1961 to 1990 (Ignagni, 1993). Ignagni tested several hypotheses, including one based on the idea of the religious mainstream, namely “that if the religious group involved in a dispute can be deemed marginal (outside the mainstream), then the Supreme Court will be more likely to uphold its free exercise claims” (Ignagni, 1993). In short, Ignagni found empirical evidence supporting that the Court favours such marginal religious groups.

The final area of importance in case analysis is the fairly well-trodden path of research that has sought to determine whether and how a judge’s faith influences their approach to deciding cases, particularly those involving moral or ethical questions where religious beliefs might play a significant role (Blake, 2011). One such study, by political science scholar William Blake, was *God Save This Honorable Court: Religion as a Source of Judicial Policy Preference* (Blake, 2011). Essentially, he extended Sisk’s ideas, arguing that if Supreme Court behaviour is structured largely by policy preferences, and one in First Amendment cases does exist, political scientists ought to consider the source of those preferences. For Blake, as is the case in this article, religion is viewed as one such force that can strongly shape a judge’s worldview and therefore their votes. Presenting a quantitative analysis using the Supreme Court Database between the 1953 and 2007 terms, Blake found that “Across a wide range of legal issues, it appears that the Catholic variable plays a role in judicial decision-making independent of ideology” (Blake, 2011). Ultimately, Catholic Justices, in particular, vote in ways that more closely adhere to the teachings of the Catholic Church than do non-Catholic Justices. It is a trend that persists even after controlling for outside factors like ideology. Additionally, for Blake, even on issues that may not have much theological difference, “religious values play a more prominent role in public life for Catholic Justices” (Blake, 2011).

Taking the issues of faith and ideology one step further, scholars Michael Bailey and Forrest Maltzman attempted to challenge the traditional belief that the personal policy preferences of the justices predominantly drive Supreme Court decisions. Instead, Bailey and Maltzman argued that legal doctrine plays a significant, albeit complex, role in shaping judicial outcomes (Bailey and Maltzman, 2008). In other words, while policy and personal preferences are undeniably influential, the interaction between these preferences and legal doctrines shapes the final judicial decision. In short, these Justices tend to exercise greater restraint and potentially have less of a desire to actively “legislate” and transform the law than some might think (which might, in the case examined by this study, explain the larger share of establishment cases as opposed to religious liberty or free exercise ones) (Bailey and Maltzman, 2008).

As a whole, these studies enrich the field of judicial behaviour analysis by illuminating the complex interplay between empiricism, religion, and the judicial process. Furthermore, every study of this type I have examined thus far, while not enough to settle the “religion” question once and for all, seems to suggest that there may be so-called “preferential” biases among the court that show their behaviours are non-random. From Sisk and Blake to Brent and Ignagni, while specific conclusions may differ, a generalisable set of dots can pretty readily tie the court to religion. While definitive, absolute certainty may never be known, the main takeaways from these three areas of analysis are perhaps best summarised by Stephen Feldman, writing, “Most people would acknowledge that religious orientation often influences an individual’s political values or preferences. Members of evangelical Protestant denominations, for example, are more likely to be conservative Republicans than liberal Democrats. Empirical studies in political science reinforce this common-sense view” (Feldman, 2006).

Fast-forwarding to today, one of the most substantive and relevant analyses ever conducted on this subject was the 2021 study, *The Roberts Court and the Transformation of Constitutional Protections for Religion: A Statistical Portrait* by Lee Epstein and Eric Posner. By examining “93 case outcomes, outcomes...consisting of 824 votes cast by 31 Justices,” mostly between 1953 and 2019, the authors aimed to “supplement the doctrinal scholarship with an empirical accounting” (Epstein and Posner, 2021). Yet, where this analysis proves most unique is how it attempts to redefine Justice’s ideological positions in multivariate analysis. For Epstein and Posner, there is a tacit understanding that judges’ ideological or policy disposition is more complex than merely conservative or liberal (Epstein and Posner, 2021). Their work frequently explores how external factors, such as public opinion and political pressures, influence the Court’s decisions on religious freedom. Epstein and Posner’s analyses provide insights into the broader patterns and trends in

the Court's handling of First Amendment cases, contributing to a deeper understanding of judicial decision-making processes in this contentious area.

Moreover, while Epstein and Posner's study is undoubtedly helpful in attempting to develop a framework for analysing the Justices, the study is limited in its sole focus on the characteristics of the judges themselves—such as ideological leanings and appointment histories—while not delving deeply into the complexities of the cases beyond a fundamental dichotomy of Free Exercise versus Establishment Clause issues. This approach can inadvertently oversimplify the multifaceted nature of religious cases before the Supreme Court. Many of these cases intertwine with other significant factors, like the petitioner's religion. Nevertheless, despite its limitations, the methods employed by Lee Epstein and Eric Posner in their study offer a robust framework for quantitative legal analysis of the Supreme Court, providing an empirical basis to assess trends and shifts in judicial behaviour and case preference over time. By quantitatively cataloguing decisions and categorising them into clear legal domains—such as Free Exercise and Establishment Clause cases—their approach allows for the aggregation and analysis of data that can reveal patterns in the Court's jurisprudence.

HYPOTHESES

With these ideas in mind, I have turned them into three specific guiding research questions, each of which holds significant implications for our understanding of the Court's decision-making process:

1. Are First Amendment objections based on religious grounds more likely to succeed than similar objections based on secular ones?
2. If such a pattern exists, which type of religious cases are benefiting?
3. Whether or not Justices are more likely to support religious objections on the whole, has the *nature* of the cases that have won changed?

Being informed by my review and research questions, I have operationalised these questions into four hypotheses to be able to fully tackle each of these research questions. These four hypotheses aim to explore how religious factors influence the outcomes of Supreme Court cases and the voting patterns of Justices, as well as how these dynamics may have evolved. Each hypothesis aims to dissect a specific aspect of the interplay between religion and judicial decision-making within the context of the US legal system.

My hypotheses are as follows:

Ha #1: All else equal, the Supreme Court is more likely to rule in favour of religious objections than secular ones.

Ha #2: Religious majority cases are more likely to succeed as opposed to those raised by religious minorities.

Ha #3: The Court's tendency to rule in favour of religious claims—especially those from majority groups—has increased over time (specifically for religious *majorities*).

Ha #4: Justices themselves are generally more inclined to support religious outcomes, with this preference growing over time (specifically for religious *majorities*).

Ha #1 attempts to determine if there is a discernible bias or preference in the Supreme Court towards cases that invoke religious rationales over those that present secular arguments. This could indicate the Court's sensitivity or deference to religious beliefs and practices when adjudicating cases, reflecting a broader judicial philosophy regarding the role of religion in public life and law. I made this prediction because, thus far, all the literature points to there being some meaningful relationship.

Ha #2 builds on this, testing the notion that petitioners from religious majorities (e.g., mainstream Christianity in the US) have a higher success rate in Court than those from minority religions (e.g. Islam, Judaism, Jehovah's Witnesses). This could suggest that prevailing societal norms or biases influence judicial outcomes, potentially reflecting greater cultural or institutional support for the beliefs of the majority religion.

Ha #3 explores the temporal dimension, suggesting that the trends identified in the first three hypotheses have become more pronounced over time. An increase could reflect changing social attitudes towards religion, shifts in the composition of the Court, or evolving legal doctrines that increasingly favour religious considerations.

Ha #4 tries to narrow the focus of Ha #3, shifting the focus away from the cases and toward the Justices. Here, the focus moves to the individual Justices' voting behaviour, hypothesising that Justices tend to support outcomes that favour religious positions when controlling for other variables. This hypothesis probes Justices' personal or ideological inclinations towards religion and how these may affect their legal judgments. Taken together, Ha #3 and Ha #4 could indicate not only a general trend towards more religion-friendly judicial outcomes but also a specific strengthening of the position of significant religions in legal conflicts, potentially at the expense of minority religions.

In all, these hypotheses are designed to thoroughly investigate the complex relationship between religion and the judiciary, offering insights into whether and how religious considerations influence legal outcomes in the Supreme Court and how these influences have evolved.

METHODS

Within this study, I employ a quantitative analysis that allows me to meticulously analyse case outcomes, scrutinise the Justices' votes, and explore the socio-legal context surrounding pivotal cases. As mentioned earlier, more broadly, I am seeking to determine the extent to which, if at all, religious preference exists within the decisions of the Supreme Court.

The dataset accounts for 105 cases (and 925 Justice votes), constituting a comprehensive aggregation of Supreme Court cases focused on religious freedom issues, meticulously compiled from various esteemed sources. This includes, but is not limited to, the Washington University of St. Louis Database, seminal studies conducted by Lee Epstein and Eric Posner, and data from Congressional Quarterly (CQ). The primary objective of assembling this dataset is to create the most accurate and contemporaneously relevant compilation of all orally argued cases from 1945 through to the term year 2022. In the interest of focusing on cases that underwent a comprehensive judicial review process, this collection deliberately excludes those cases that were resolved without the benefit of oral argument.

For this analysis, I use an ordinary least-squares (OLS) model centred around five key variables labelled as follows: case outcome, case impact (which, together with case outcome, determines case nature), issue focus, case awareness, and case salience.

While the variables themselves, how they were chosen, and how they are measured are defined in greater detail in the *Appendix*, the two most important to understand are "Case Outcome" and "Case Impact." Case outcome is a variable of my own creation and consists of two categories, "1. Religious wins" and "0. Religious losses" defined based on the ultimate outcome of the case. Religious wins (or, in simpler terms, pro-religion outcomes) are categorised as if they favour a religious organisation or religious outcome (typically the plaintiff in a Free Exercise clause case and the defendant—the state—in an Establishment clause case). Religious losses are defined as any outcome to the contrary. Case impact, by contrast, is defined as the group or groups most positively affected by a given ruling and is divided into two categories: "1. Pro-Majority" and "0. Anti-Majority." The variable "1. Pro-Majority" means that the ruling was in favour of the largest Christian American mainstream, while the variable "0. Anti-Majority" means that the ruling went to the contrary. The reason for this distinction is that the religion clauses of the First Amendment are fundamentally different when talking in terms of religious minorities (like the Amish, Muslims, or Jewish people) as opposed to the widespread and all-encompassing mainstream Christian organisations, practices, and values that dominate the country. I seek to understand how distinct each group truly is.

For this study, each case and Justice has been coded along these various variables. For instance, in a "1. Religion Wins," "1. Majority Wins" case, a Justice voting in favour would be coded as "11" and against "00." By contrast, in a "1. Religion Wins," "0. Anti-Majority" case, a Justice voting in favour would be coded as "10" and likewise "01" if they voted against.

For the case of simplicity, for further rationale as to why I chose each variable, and as a reference, please see the *Appendix* for my codebook. Finally, for understanding the different forms that cases can take, below is a simple *Outcome-Impact matrix* summarising the case nature to help break everything down:

Outcome/Impact	Pro-Majority (1)	Anti-Majority (0)
Religious Win (1)	Religion Wins, Mainstream Wins (11) <i>Ex: Kennedy v. Bremerton School District (2022)</i> (45 Cases)	Religion Wins, Mainstream Loses (10) <i>Ex: Wisconsin v. Yoder (1972)</i> (19 Cases)
Religious Loss (0)	Religion Loses, Mainstream Wins (01) <i>Ex: Braunfeld v. Brown (1960)</i> (12 Cases)	Religion Loses, Mainstream Loses (00) <i>Ex: Lemon v. Kurtzman (1971)</i> (29 Cases)

Figure 1. Outcome-Impact Matrix.

My first two models assessed decisions on the case level. Of these two regressions, the first treated the case outcome as the dependent variable (DV), with the other four as independent variables (IVs). The second model removed the case outcome and looked solely at the case impact (turning it from an IV in the first regression to the DV), with the other three remaining as IVs. The final two models essentially repeated the processes from the first two, but instead of looking at the case level, went all the way down to the Justice-level, assessing Justice votes for/against religion (case outcome) as well as how they voted in terms of the more significant case impact.

In addition to these measures, the final two models (focusing on Justices) introduced two additional variables to control for ideology. The first is the party-of-the-appointing-president model, which assigns the jurist to the political party of the President who appointed them. However, while useful, this model is imperfect. Justices David Souter and John Paul Stevens proved challenging to code because both Justices, although appointed by Republican Presidents, came to be perceived as very liberal members of the Court (Rundle, 2009). Solid arguments can be made for various coding decisions for these Justices. On one hand, whether these Justices had any meaningful affiliation with the Republican Party remains unclear, and they may have self-identified as independents or even as Democrats (Greenhouse, 2019). On the other hand, the objective of this methodology is to distinguish partisanship from ideology, and thus coding these two Justices as Democrats based on their ideology could itself potentially risk conflating these two variables.

To account for such discrepancies, I have included a secondary control for ideology, the Bridge Ideal-Point model created by Dr Michael Bailey (Bailey, 2013). The ideal-point model for tracking the ideology of Supreme Court Justices represents a sophisticated approach to quantitatively measuring Justices' ideological positions based on their judicial decisions. This model is part of a broader set of methods used by political scientists and legal scholars to estimate the ideological leanings of court members, aiming to provide a more nuanced understanding of how personal beliefs and values might influence legal judgments (Bailey, 2013).

The reasoning for tracking Justice votes in a study primarily dedicated to case outcomes is twofold. The first is for the sake of completeness. Justice votes and case outcomes are two sides of the same coin, and it would be improper to examine one without confirming that the other matched (or if it told a completely different story). The second and more important reason is due to sample size. Cases involving religious establishment and liberty issues only comprise about 105 cases over the last eighty years. As a problem of regression analysis, sample sizes of 50 or even 100 are suggested if not required to be able to have any shred of confidence in the results. When broken down to specific chief Justice eras, these numbers become even more problematic, with both the Vinson and Warren courts hovering around the single digits (7 and 11, respectively). This means that even if the *overall* case outcomes *barely* meet the generally accepted sample size for a regression model, any, if not every, result within and across individual courts is tenuous at best. As a result, the only regression that can (even somewhat) confidently be run on the case outcome is of the 105-observation sample in its entirety, failing to delineate effectively between eras. Tracking

Justice votes offers a somewhat indirect yet insightful method of addressing this issue—expanding our sample size from 105 data points to well over 900, with all but Vinson (65) effectively reaching the recommended 100-sample threshold (with Warren just shy at 97). This expansion allows us to better track differences between and across eras. It allows for far greater certainty and robustness from the results that would not be achieved from a straight-line high-level case outcome assessment. In short, the only way to truly reach any certainty about what is going on in the court at the case level is to go one level deeper and reverse-engineer a sample base that can provide meaningful takeaways.

ANALYSIS:

Part 1 - High-Level Trends:

The past five Supreme Court eras have been the Vinson (1946 -1953), Warren (1953 - 1969), Burger (1969 - 1986), Rehnquist (1986 - 2005) and Roberts (2005 – Present) Courts. In recent years, the United States Supreme Court’s approach to religious cases has undergone notable shifts, reflecting broader trends in jurisprudence and societal attitudes toward the intersection of law and religious practice. A high-level analysis of the Court’s decisions and case composition in religious cases, particularly under Chief Justice John Roberts’s stewardship, reveals three significant trends that merit closer examination.

Firstly, the Roberts Court has demonstrated a marked propensity to take up a substantially higher volume of cases concerning the Free Exercise Clause than its predecessors, most notably the Burger Court. Figure 2 shows the breakdown of these issues by era.

Figure 2. Issue Focus by Court.

From the Vinson Court of the 1940s to the Roberts Court today, there has been a notable departure from the earlier Court’s focus on Establishment Clause cases (71% in the Burger Court compared to just 24% for Roberts), indicating a re-evaluation of priorities, emphasising individuals’ rights to practice their religion freely.

At face value, this pattern suggests that the Roberts court is taking and deciding more free exercise cases, a shift that marks not just a change in direction but a fundamental reorientation of the Court’s stance on religious freedom. This shift is interesting because all three preceding eras within Figure 2 (Warren, Burger, and Rehnquist) show a roughly equal and majority share of Establishment Clause cases taken up as opposed to free exercise ones. Interestingly enough, as mentioned in the Bailey and Maltzman study,

this larger share of establishment cases may reflect the Justices' tendency to exercise greater restraint rather than play a more active role in reshaping the law (Bailey and Maltzman, 2008).

While it should be noted that Bailey and Maltzman's study was published in 2008 and did not include the Roberts Court, if one operates under the idea (like Bailey and Maltzman)—that legal doctrine and political philosophy were guiding factors in giving Justices a greater disposition towards exercising restraint and maintaining the status quo as opposed to creating or transforming law (hence the greater inclination toward establishment cases as opposed to religious liberty and free exercise ones)—it could be argued that the Roberts Court, by comparison, appears more “free” (or less-restrained) than their counterparts (Bailey and Maltzman, 2008). In the figure above, the Roberts Court is alone in seeming to have a strong propensity for selecting cases on free exercise as opposed to establishment grounds. Thus, this shift is notable because it *might* suggest a greater eagerness among the current Justices to try and change the law or make new laws concerning religious liberties and First Amendment cases—a tendency that may not have existed in the past.

Second, the popular notion that the Roberts Court represents a break in the development of religion cases is amply supported by the data. Figure 3 shows the Chief Justice era's breakdown of pro-religion and anti-religion case outcomes.

Figure 3. Religious Success by Court.

Over the examined period, the Court ruled in favour of religion approximately 60% of the time. Broken down by issue across each of the first four chief Justices, win rates do not differ significantly for Free Exercise Clause cases (64%) and Establishment Clause cases (58%). Additionally, as can be seen in the figure above, across the nearly 50 years of the Warren, Burger, and Rehnquist courts, the religious side prevailed about half the time, with gradually increasing success. In contrast, this win rate jumps up to 81% in the Roberts Court. Accordingly, an overarching analysis indicates that claims rooted in religious liberty are winning at a far greater rate on the Roberts Court than in previous eras, suggesting that Ha #1 and even Ha #3 have some merit. At least on the surface, this trend suggests a judiciary increasingly sympathetic to arguments framed within the context of protecting or expanding religious freedoms, which may reflect changing interpretations of the First Amendment or shifts in the Court's ideological makeup.

Third, and perhaps most controversially, there appears to be a discernible pattern where mainstream Christian groups find more favourable outcomes in their litigation efforts before the Roberts Court. Figure 4 shows the breakdown of pro-majority and anti-majority case outcomes by the Chief Justice era.

Figure 4. Mainstream Christian Success by Court.

Among the three earliest chiefs—Vinson, Warren, and Burger—religious majorities are, at best, able to win no more than 45% of the time. With Rehnquist, this number crosses the midpoint for the first time (58%) only to jump again by the Roberts Court (66%). Indeed, at a high level, there is at least an apparent trend of mainstream Christianity. At face value, this provides at least some evidence for Ha #1.

Such a trend could also indicate the Court's shifting attitudinal and political priorities to meet a new agenda. These changes in case composition and outcomes in the Roberts Court could directly reflect the ideological and personal beliefs of its Justices. Rather than being solely guided by legal precedents or the merits of cases, the Justices' decisions, including which cases to hear and how to rule on them, could be influenced by their preferences and attitudes toward issues of religious freedom and expression. The Court's shift in political and ideological direction is evident in its recent case selections, most notably in 303 *Creative v. Elenis* (2023). The case involved Lorie Smith, a Colorado-based web designer and owner of 303 Creative LLC, who sought to challenge a Colorado anti-discrimination law pre-emptively. Smith, who wanted to expand her business to include wedding websites, argued that being compelled to create websites for same-sex weddings would violate her First Amendment rights to free speech and free exercise of religion. The Colorado Anti-Discrimination Act (CADA) prohibited businesses open to the public from discriminating against customers based on sexual orientation (among other characteristics), effectively requiring businesses like Smith's to provide services equally to all customers, regardless of the owner's personal beliefs (Jacobson, 2024).

This case was problematic because it presented a hypothetical scenario in that Smith had not yet been asked to create a website for a same-sex wedding, nor had she been subject to any enforcement action under CADA (Jacobson, 2024). Her legal challenge was pre-emptive, aiming to secure a ruling allowing her to refuse such services in the future without facing legal repercussions for discrimination. This pre-emptive challenge sets the stage for the Supreme Court to address the broader and highly contentious issues of religious freedom, free speech, and anti-discrimination protections within the context of public accommodations, which she did in a 6-3 victory (Jacobson, 2024).

At first glance, there is strong evidence for the notion of the court experiencing a religious slant (with its trajectory increasing over time)—much in line with Ha's #1 to Ha's #3. In all, much of the Court's case composition, examining the Supreme Court's recent jurisprudence under Chief Justice John Roberts, reveals high-level shifts in the handling of religion cases, marked by three key trends. First, there is a notable increase in the Court's engagement with Free Exercise Clause cases, diverging from the historical focus on Establishment Clause issues that characterised the Burger Court, suggesting a switch from more traditional government oversight cases to religious protection or even advocacy. Second, the success rate of religious liberty claims has markedly increased, indicating a judicial environment more favourable to

arguments advocating for expanding religious freedoms, in line with Ha’s #1 and #3. Lastly, mainstream Christian groups are achieving greater success in their legal battles before the Roberts Court compared to previous eras-in line with Ha’s #2 and #3. Such findings raise important questions about the balance the Court is striking between religious freedom and religious neutrality and equality principles, suggesting that such a trend may be even more pronounced than earlier scholarship thought. Together, these trends highlight the evolving dynamics of the Supreme Court’s approach to religious cases and prompt whether the weight of significance testing genuinely backs such surface-level trends or if this is instead purely random.

Part 2 - Case Outcome:

Among the earliest regressions on case outcome, the two models yielded one significant result. The two OLS regressions for the entire sample were tested at the 5% significance level assessing the dependent variables of case outcome and later case impact. The resulting estimators, significant results, and their accompanying t-statistics are as follows:

Figure 5. OLS Regression of Pro-Religion (Cases)

	All Eras
Issue Focus	-0.66 -0.588
Mainstream	0.382* 3.867
NYT (Awareness)	-0.017 -0.141
CQ (Sallience)	0.012 0.089
Vinson	X
Warren	-0.469 -1.951
Burger	-0.389 -1.923
Rehnquist	-0.369 -1.792
Roberts	-0.095 -0.393
Constant	0.753* 3.535
Observations	105

*Indicates $p > 0.05$

Figure 6. OLS Regression of Pro-Majority (Cases)

	All Eras
Issue Focus	-0.124 -1.006
NYT (Awareness)	-0.131 -0.978
CQ (Sallience)	-0.040 -0.263
Vinson	X
Warren	0.136 0.512
Burger	-0.027 -0.121
Rehnquist	-0.105 0.464
Roberts	-0.064 -0.241
Constant	0.566* 2.494
Observations	105

*Indicates $p > 0.05$

Era	Count
Vinson	7
Warren	11
Burger	35
Rehnquist	31
Roberts	21
Observations	105

Within the two models, the variable “chief” seeks to account for discrepancies by comparing the four succeeding eras against the Vinson to assess for differences across time, using the first period (Vinson) to try and assess for within-group differences. As a result, the Vinson Court is omitted, with the variable “chief” being split into the four variables titled “Warren,” “Burger,” “Rehnquist,” and “Roberts.”⁴ This

⁴ **Note:** Based on seminal works from scholars like Epstein and Posner, there is an argument to be made that the Warren Court may be a more appropriate baseline. Anecdotally, this is mainly because most people already think of the liberalism of the Warren Court as the kind of “default” for the Court in a way often forgotten about with the Vinson Court. As a result, some would argue that the better fit for our natural, cultural way of thinking would be to compare each era to the Warren Court. That said, in Figures 5 and 6, the variable “Warren” was also tested as the baseline for the within-group comparisons rather than “Vinson,” but the analysis did not yield conclusive results. Like the “Vinson” baseline above, none of the other four eras were statistically significant.

approach focuses on changes from an initial baseline and streamlines parameter estimation to clearly illustrate the shifts or trends over time by comparing subsequent data points to a common starting point. Nevertheless, even when comparing terms, the results are inconclusive at best, especially for the second model in Figure 6. Only Ha #2 can be accepted (and tenuously at that), with Figure 5 showing that there is a statistically significant (slight) pro-majority preference in religious cases else equal.

Additionally, while the results were inconclusive across the board, the variables generated from “Warren,” “Burger,” and “Rehnquist” are all *nearly* significant, with p-values ranging between 5-8% and t-statistics of -1.951, -1.923, and -1.792, respectively. In other words, even if these terms were not significant at the 5% level, it should be noted that they are *weakly* significant and pass at the 10% level. Were we to accept these results at the 10% level, it could be said that the three courts show a demonstrable anti-religion shift from the Warren - showcasing a decline in religious preference across time that would theoretically go against Ha #4. Taking this contention to the logical extreme, Ha #4 would simultaneously be boosted since the *current* Court (Roberts) is the lone outlier from such anti-religious certainty. Moreover, the reason that the “Warren,” “Burger,” and “Rehnquist” terms are only weakly correlated rather than showing a statistically significant relationship may be simply a function of the limited number of observations, floating at or around the single digits for the Vinson (7) and Warren (11) Courts, respectively. Nevertheless, these numbers should be interpreted with extreme apprehension; this study was conducted at the 5% level, so for our purposes, while their significance levels are certainly worth mentioning as *potentially* indicative of some trends, they are still inconclusive.

Although the first two regressions on case outcome results lacked widespread statistical significance, these inconclusive results don’t necessarily mean that Ha’s #1 to Ha’s #4 are categorically rejected. As discussed in the methods section, a smaller sample size in regression analysis introduces a higher degree of uncertainty to the results, primarily due to increased standard errors and wider confidence intervals. With fewer data points, the variability of the sample mean from the population mean becomes larger, affecting the precision with which population parameters can be estimated. In short, it is unclear whether we might actually be committing a Type I error—that is, being led to reject the null hypotheses (and say there is *not* in fact a religious preference present on the Court) when one might actually exist. The rationale behind this is reflected in the larger standard errors associated with the regression coefficients, signalling more uncertainty about the estimated effects of the predictors on the outcome variable. This means there’s less certainty about the exact value of these parameters, making definitive conclusions about the relationship between variables more challenging. In simple terms, the smaller the sample, the less confident one can be in the stability and generalisability of the regression results.

Placed into the context of the regressions in Figures 5 and 6, just by looking at the table, the total count represents a meagre 105 observations. Even with the eras compared against a baseline of the Vinson court to account for this smaller sample size, we are placing the data equivalent of a band-aid on an amputee. All that can truly be said about this are (very tentatively) two major takeaways. First, a (tenuous) yet significant relationship exists between religious wins and mainstream Christian wins, validating Ha #2. Second, among the data overall across both regressions, the general direction of the estimators on issue focus, mainstream Christian wins, NYT [The New York Times] (awareness), and CQ [Congressional Quarterly] (Salience) all show an interesting yet non-significant shift both in magnitude and direction from Vinson to Roberts. While, for the reasons mentioned previously, these trends cannot be verified on these two regressions alone, it is a takeaway that merits greater examination within Part 3’s expanded dataset.

Part 3 - Justice Votes:

With case outcomes alone proving insufficient, the analysis must now shift to the most natural explanation for the transformation of religious jurisprudence: changes in the personnel of the Court. The same parameters were applied to Justice votes as to case outcomes at-large for these regressions in Part 2. Additionally, as previously outlined in the methods section, two controls for Justice ideology, labelled “Party (President)” and “Ideology (Ideal Point)”, were added. Once again, the regressions both for the entire sample set and each era were tested at the 5% significance level, assessing the dependent variable of Justice votes in Case Outcome and Case Impact, and the resulting estimators, significant results, and their accompanying t-statistics are as follows:

	All Eras	Vison	Warren	Burger	Rehnquist	Roberts
Issue Focus	0.173*	0.025	0.181	0.057	0.096	0.198*
	5.704	0.161	1.719	0.971	1.581	3.203
Mainstream	0.394*	-0.411*	0.323*	0.405*	0.505*	0.493*
	12.469	-3.446	3.152	7.111	8.248	7.065
Ideology (Party)	0.034	0.173	0.123	-0.056	0.247*	-0.028
	0.881	0.983	1.272	-0.864	3.116	-0.162
Ideology (Model)	0.043*	-0.093	-0.061*	0.1*	-0.087	0.082
	2.104	-1.953	-1.125	2.827	-1.948	0.899
NYT (Awareness)	-0.017	0.179	-0.343*	-0.028	0.026	0.063
	-0.449	1.283	-2.018	-0.458	0.422	0.995
CQ (Salience)	-0.017	0.255	-0.18	-0.061	0	-0.184*
	-0.723	1.278	-1.34	-0.779	0.003	-2.354
Vinson	X	X	X	X	X	X
Warren	-0.343*	X	X	X	X	X
	-4.385					
Burger	-0.31*	X	X	X	X	X
	-4.628					
Rehnquist	-0.251*	X	X	X	X	X
	-3.785					
Roberts	-0.15*	X	X	X	X	X
	-2.209					
Constant	0.318*	0.794*	0.51*	0.385*	0.127	0.399*
	8.486	5.231	2.765	5.387	1.458	3.55
Observations	925	61	97	309	277	181

*Indicates $p > 0.05$

Figure 7. OLS Regression of Pro-Religion (Justice Votes).

	All Eras	Vinson	Warren	Burger	Rehnquist	Roberts
Issue Focus	-0.033	-0.281	0.216*	-0.089	-0.151*	-0.019
	-0.968	-1.665	2.051	-1.521	-2.543	-0.279
Ideology (Party)	-0.066	-0.291	0.055	-0.229*	-0.112	0.157
	-1.598	-1.493	0.553	-3.561	-1.428	0.825
Ideology (Model)	0.244*	0.016	0.125*	0.297*	0.313*	0.172
	11.932	0.3	2.338	9.416	7.787	1.75
NYT (Awareness)	-0.129*	-0.292	-0.472*	-0.086	-0.244*	-0.135*
	-3.642	-1.907	-2.384	-1.425	-4.045	-2.007
CQ (Salience)	0.153*	0.889*	-0.262	-0.023	0.079	0.529*
	3.816	4.668	-1.951	-0.285	1.297	7.104
Vinson	X	X	X	X	X	X
Warren	0.328*	X	X	X	X	X
	4.033					
Burger	0.149*	X	X	X	X	X
	2.135					
Rehnquist	0.097	X	X	X	X	X
	1.399					
Roberts	0.128	X	X	X	X	X
	1.804					
Constant	0.416*	0.574*	0.906*	0.705*	0.682*	0.153
	6.269	3.753	5.569	11.81	9.004	1.264
Observations	925	61	97	309	277	181

*Indicates $p > 0.05$

Figure 8. OLS Regression of Pro-Majority (Justice Votes).

While again both models looked for within-group differences based on the variable “chief” (split across the four Chief Justices compared to Vinson), the expanded set also has the added benefit of assessing between-g.⁵ That is to say, assessing the individual trends and behaviours of each Chief Justice’s era

⁵ **Note:** Again, in Figures 7 and 8, the variable “Warren” was also tested as the baseline for the within-group comparisons rather than “Vinson,” but the analysis did not yield strong results. For instance, within 7, only “Roberts” and “Vinson” were found to be significant compared to all four eras when using “Vinson” as the baseline.

individually. As shown in Figures 7 and 8 above, the expanded 925 size dataset regressing Justice votes rather than individual cases yielded a staggering 34 significant results (split 18 and 16 respectively). To start, the two models provide mixed support for Ha's #3 and #4. Initially, they signal a shift more *against* religion, yet of the religious cases taken up (as seen in the "all eras" line of Figure 8), there is notably greater support for religious majorities among the succeeding two eras, following a shift in voting behaviour in favour towards religion. This argument is supported when assessing their relationships individually across the following five regressions. All four succeeding eras show markedly stronger pro-majority favouritism compared to the Vinson Court (going from the *negative* at -0.411 in the Vinson Court to a *positive* relationship represented by the estimator 0.493). Additionally, every era shows a significant relationship between religious outcomes and the Christian mainstream—again supporting Ha #1 and Ha #2 that such a preference exists and exists for religious *majorities* specifically. However, that estimator flips from being in support of religious minorities (coded as anti-majority) among the Vinson court at -0.411 to religious-majority backing in the positive direction of 0.505 and 0.493 among the Rehnquist and Roberts courts, respectively—implying that the outcomes show significantly more support for Christian mainstream today than in the 1940s and 50s.

Another interesting takeaway is that the Roberts Court appears to be acutely sensitive to so-called "big" cases—cases on CQ's landmark list and/or ones that make the front page of the New York Times. Across both models, three out of the four estimators between the variables CQ and NYT were significant for the Roberts Court (as opposed to just 1/8 for the other four eras), with the CQ estimator in the second model reaching a whopping 0.529—meaning that given that a particular case before the Court is labelled by CQ as a "landmark case," with a one-unit increase in salience we see a 0.529 point increase in the probability that the Christian mainstream comes out on top. Anecdotally, this makes sense. After all, Justices, like everyone else, do not operate in a vacuum.

As shocking as the idea of a not-perfectly neutral judiciary may be, it makes sense. It's evident that, like most people, Justices (who sit at the very forefront of government) are at least somewhat aware of the political headwinds of the times. At the same time, more significant cases can carry greater weight, and that, in turn, means a greater impact for whichever way they may rule. As a result, it is understandable that if Justices genuinely feel strongly about religious liberties and free exercise, they would have the *greatest* disposition to support such claims in the cases that matter the most (Epstein and Posner, 2021).

Finally, across nearly every era, both for religious wins as well as wins for the Christian mainstream, both ideology variables appear to play a substantial role—with the ideal-point estimator showcasing statistically significant rightward leans of 0.125, 0.297, and 0.313 from the Warren, Burger and Rehnquist Courts, respectively, in Figure 8. More precisely, it appears that more modern and conservative Justices tend to (at least somewhat) vote in increasing favour of *both* religion and the Christian mainstream—in line with Ha #4. Taken one step further, looking at this behaviour between Justices and across Courts only makes this relationship more apparent. Figure 9 ranks the judges by the percentage of pro-religion votes, with the current Roberts court highlighted in yellow. For this analysis, a minimum criterion of five votes was set to compare win rates among Justices properly. As a result, while Justices Murphy, Barrett, Brown-Jackson, Goldberg, Fortas, and Rutledge may have voted on one or multiple cases during this period, they were excluded from the summary statistics.

Within 8, all four eras were found to be significant when using "Warren" as the baseline—yielding a total of 6/8 Courts across both models yielding significant results (the same as the "Vinson" baseline).

	% Religion	Pro- Majority	Pro- Difference	NYT	CQ	Ideal-Point (Average)	Party	Count
Kavanaugh	100.00%	77.78%	22.22%	6	8	0.7687	R	9
Gorsuch	91.67%	83.33%	8.34%	8	11	1.0153	R	12
Roberts	90.48%	76.19%	14.29%	12	15	0.6533	R	21
Alito	90.00%	80.00%	10.00%	12	15	1.1310	R	20
Thomas	89.74%	82.05%	7.69%	26	30	1.4535	R	39
Vinson	83.33%	50.00%	33.33%	2	1	0.4136	D	6
Reed	83.33%	50.00%	33.33%	2	1	0.7462	D	6
Minton	80.00%	40.00%	40.00%	2	1	0.5331	D	5
Scalia	79.49%	79.49%	0.00%	20	22	1.1843	R	39
Burger	77.14%	68.57%	8.57%	15	6	0.9364	R	35
Kagan	70.59%	47.06%	23.53%	12	15	-0.7189	D	17
Kennedy	70.27%	67.57%	2.70%	22	25	0.4226	R	37
Rehnquist	69.35%	87.10%	-17.75%	28	24	1.3740	R	62
White	66.67%	71.93%	-5.26%	27	14	0.1572	D	57
Stewart	66.67%	45.45%	21.22%	18	4	0.1514	R	33
Frankfurter	66.67%	41.67%	25.00%	6	1	0.3380	D	12
Burton	66.67%	33.33%	33.34%	2	1	0.5221	D	6
Breyer	61.76%	44.12%	17.64%	21	26	-0.6499	D	34
O'Connor	57.78%	53.33%	4.45%	24	23	0.5605	R	45
Clark	57.14%	42.86%	14.28%	9	3	0.2255	D	14
Black	52.38%	42.86%	9.52%	15	4	-1.6143	D	21
Powell	51.43%	51.43%	0.00%	12	6	0.4910	R	35
Whittaker	50.00%	66.67%	-16.67%	4	0	0.5902	R	6
Warren	50.00%	50.00%	0.00%	10	2	-0.8481	R	12
Blackmun	49.02%	29.41%	19.61%	22	14	-0.0690	R	51
Harlan	46.67%	60.00%	-13.33%	13	3	0.7701	R	15
Brennan	46.67%	21.67%	25.00%	28	12	-1.1310	R	60
Marshall	44.90%	22.45%	22.45%	19	8	-1.4716	D	49
Douglas	41.38%	10.34%	31.04%	19	5	-1.9024	D	29
Sotomayor	40.00%	20.00%	20.00%	12	15	-1.1665	D	20
Souter	36.84%	21.05%	15.79%	14	15	0.5237	R	19
Jackson	33.33%	33.33%	0.00%	2	1	0.5262	D	6
Stevens	29.31%	24.14%	5.17%	25	23	-1.0237	R	58
Ginsburg	23.33%	10.00%	13.33%	17	23	-0.9320	D	30

Excluded: Murphy, Barrett, Brown-Jackson, Goldberg, Fortas, and Rutledge (Min. 5 Cases)

Figure 9. Summary Statistic Ranking of Justices by Pro-Religion Votes.

As shown in the figure above, the top five most pro-religion Justices all currently sit on the Roberts Court, they are Republican appointees, and they are all ideologically conservative, with Kavanaugh leading the way at a perfect 100%. The top five also sit at or near the top of the list in the percentage of votes for religious majorities. Looking just below, this number jumps to 7 of the top 12 when we include legacy justices like Scalia and Kennedy, who had previously sat in the Roberts court. Even a more “liberal” Justice like Kagan cracks the top 12. While there is not a “perfect” line of all the oldest Justices being the most anti-religion and every single one of the more recent Justices becoming more pro-religious and pro-majority than their predecessors, as would be ideally in line with Ha’s #3-4, the results do show the oldest and newest Courts (Roberts and Vinson) operating at the extremes—with the Roberts Court being the outlier from the pack with the most religious fervour. As a result, it is fair to say that while not perfectly linear over time, since they are supported by the notable shift of the most recent Court, Ha’s #3-4 are supported at least in part.

Going further across the table, even more patterns emerge. First, it appears that Republican and conservative Justices are more pro-religion than other Justices (taking 8 out of the top 12 spots). At the same time, the Roberts Court appears both the most polarised as well as the most pro-religion court, with their difference between pro-religion and pro-majority percentages placing them all at or near zero (like Scalia at a perfect 0%)—implying nearly every vote cast in favour of religion was one in favour of the Christian mainstream. Additionally, there appears to be a somewhat stark liberal divide between Justices Sotomayor and Ginsburg (along with our aforementioned two “liberal” republican Justices Stevens and Souter) sitting near the bottom of the ranking with some of the most significant differences between pro-

religion votes and pro-majority votes cast—implying that when these more liberal Justices do cast religious votes, they are in service of religious *minorities*.

Additionally, although a substantial overlap exists between pro-religion and pro-mainstream Christians, certain deviations stand out. Kagan and Breyer, both liberal Justices, are relatively high on the list under the pro-religion variable (70% and 62%) but notably drop for the pro-mainstream Christian variable (47% and 44%), as expected. Anecdotally, this makes a little bit of sense, as Democratic and liberal Justices often (particularly before the Roberts Court) tended to cast pro-religion votes in cases involving non-mainstream religions. Cases like *Trump v Hawaii* (2018) illustrate this pattern (Epstein and Posner, 2021). The conservative Justices rejected religion in favour of national security and presidential power—but it was Muslim, not Christian religion. The liberals sided with Muslims, a frequently targeted minority religious group. By contrast, the pattern then reverses for the pandemic cases. The conservative Justices side with mainly (but not entirely) mainstream Christian organisations (but also Jewish), while the liberals side with the government (Epstein and Posner, 2021).

Taken together, there are a few key takeaways from the analysis in part 3. First, there appears to be a statistically significant relationship at the 5% level between voting for religion and political party/ideology. These trends support ha's #1-4, which outline a religious preference, a preference specifically for religious majorities, and that a preference exists among the Justices as individuals. This holds regardless of whether the political party is the Justice's party or the appointing president's party. However, the differences are statistically significant only for the Roberts Court Justices. In the earlier courts, the partisan divide did not map as clearly into pro- and anti-religion votes as Figures 7 and 8 show. At the same time, on average, Justices are significantly more likely to vote for religion in free-exercise cases than in establishment cases. That gap exists for religious wins and losses across every era. Still, the gap in the data is significant only for the Roberts Court (towards free exercise) in the first model (Figure 7) and the Warren and Rehnquist Courts (in strikingly opposite directions) in the second (Figure 8). This suggests at least some semblance of a change in religious policy and prioritisation among the courts across eras (somewhat in line with Ha's #3-4).

CONCLUSION

In summary, the goal of this study was to empirically determine whether religious preferences can be quantitatively demonstrated within judicial decision-making in First Amendment religious freedom cases, and to what extent, if any, such preferences exist on the Supreme Court in particular. This research was undertaken due to the rising number of religious cases being heard by the Court and the increasing public perception that the Court might have a pro-religion bias. By statistically analysing a comprehensive dataset that includes judges' ideological leanings, case type, and external pressures, the study aimed to provide a robust understanding of the factors influencing judicial outcomes in religious freedom cases.

Moving towards the key takeaways, the primary finding of this study is that **all else equal, a statistically significant religious preference does exist in the Roberts Court**. In addition, based on the analysis, the set hypotheses were, for the most part, validated. To start, Figures 5, 7, and 8 showed that petitioners raising objections on religious grounds were, in fact, more likely to garner case “wins” and justice “votes” to a statistically significant degree—validating Ha #1. At the same time, across those three models, there was a statistically significant finding for religious objections, particularly those tied to preserving the Christian mainstream (Ha #2), both backed by the trends outlined in Figures 2-4. Third, Figures 7 and 8 showed that all else equal, Justices—particularly conservative ones—were likelier to vote in favour of religious outcomes (drawing a stark contrast to the liberal Justices who voted at higher rates in cases involving religious minorities), validating Ha #4. Such a preference was most demonstrable among the Roberts Court, as outlined in Figure 9.

Ha's #3 (and to some extent Ha #4), on the other hand, yielded somewhat mixed results. As mentioned earlier, while there is a slightly apparent increase in the propensity of religious success over time (seen in the high-level trends from Figures 2, 3, and 4), this straightforward conclusion begins to waver under the scrutiny of the OLS regressions in Figures 5-8. Thus, while we cannot say that there exists a “perfect” or “gradual” shift over time that starts with the Vinson Court as the most “anti-religion” or “anti-majority,” followed by the Warren, Burger, Rehnquist, and Roberts in that order, what we can take away is perhaps even more important. Figures 7 and 8 show the Roberts Court as a unique outlier among the eras, a fact supported in Figure 9, where the top 5 Justices in terms of pro-religion votes and 8 of the top 12 were all current or former members of the Roberts Court (with all but Justice Kagan ranking near the top the in

pro-majority votes). Thus, while we cannot accept Ha's #3 and #4 in their entirety, we can confidently say that the Roberts Court represents a *seismic shift* from Courts of the past.

In short, the current Court reflects a notably more pro-religious slant than its predecessors while simultaneously having a historically high degree of friendliness toward the Christian Mainstream. A conclusion that is just as, if not more significant, of a takeaway than if we accepted Ha's #3 and #4 outright.

In many respects, these findings are a reason for concern. While it is true that Justices can and do vote based on the rule of law, the data suggests a significant shift in court decisions on religious cases over time can be described by ideological disagreements and evolving religious priorities. The data shows an evolving judicial environment that is increasingly receptive to religious claims. This could reflect a shifting legal interpretation favouring a broad understanding of religious or ideological freedom and an ideal world the Court is driving toward. Cases like *303*, *Kennedy*, and even *Bruen* provide specific proof of this.

Additionally, observing that cases raised by religious majorities are more successful than those by minorities suggests a potential bias in favour of the dominant religious group. This could imply that the Court's decisions are influenced by these groups' societal prevalence or political power, or it might reflect deeper cultural biases that align with the majority's religious viewpoints. Finally, since Justices are more likely to vote in favour of religious outcomes, it might suggest that personal beliefs or the broader political-ideological climate influence judicial decision-making. This would support the idea that the Justices' decisions are at least partially driven by their perspectives on religion's role in public life rather than strictly neutral interpretations of the law.

That said, given the increase in these trends over time, it's evident that the Supreme Court is becoming more aligned with a perspective favouring religious considerations in its rulings (specifically that of the Christian mainstream). This could be due to various factors, including changes in the Court's composition, evolving societal norms regarding the place of religion in public life, or a deliberate strategy by religious groups to seek more favourable outcomes through litigation.

Looking forward, future studies could aim to build off of this work in one of two ways. First, a closer examination of judicial opinions is paramount. These opinions provide a wealth of insights into the Justices' reasoning, allowing researchers to parse out subtle indicators of religious influence. Assessment of Justice's faith and devoutness could also go a long way to understanding these implications and assessing these Justices as people. Secondly, developing a methodology to weigh the significance and ideological direction of each opinion relative to each Justice's overall ideology would offer a more precise measure of the impact of religious beliefs on legal reasoning. This would involve not just a binary assessment of whether an opinion leans conservative or liberal but a nuanced analysis that considers the depth and nature of its ideological implications and how they track compared to previous ones. This is because ideological rulings can be more neatly mapped over time to better understand the extremity of the situation, rather than the fact that the preference exists alone.

Ultimately, by incorporating these dimensions, future research can provide a more detailed and insightful analysis of the role of religious preference in the Supreme Court's operations. And ultimately, is that not what a prudent analysis of the Supreme Court should be concerned with?

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APPENDIX (Figure 10). CODEBOOK

Variable	Description
Issue Focus	This is used to control for differences between establishment and free-exercise clause cases due to the fundamental differences between the two types and how they have been viewed over the years. Coded as “o” for Establishment Clause and “1” for Free Exercise in cases in which at least four Justices considered the Free Exercise or Establishment Clause to be the primary issue and/or their reasoning for taking up the case
Case Outcome	Coded as “1” for Religious wins and “o” for Religious losses, which are defined based on the ultimate outcome of the case—that is, how the simple majority of Justices voted for/against religious organisation or religious outcome (typically but not always the plaintiff in a Free Exercise clause case and the defendant—the state—in an Establishment clause case unless said case was brought by a separate religious party)
Case Impact	Coded as “1” for a Pro-Majority ruling and “o” for an Anti-Majority one. The term “Pro-Majority” means that the ruling was in favour of the larger Christian American mainstream, while “Anti-Majority” means that the ruling went to the contrary.
Case Awareness (NYT)	I include this variable to help control for differences between cases the public is aware of (that may or may not exert public opinion and pressure) compared to the lesser-known cases that may face less public scrutiny. Case Awareness is defined as whether the decision was reported on the front page of the New York Times on the day after it was issued. If a case was featured on the front page of the Times, it was coded as “1” and consequently, if not coded as a “o.”
Case Salience (CQ)	Similar to “Case Awareness,” this is an additional control for public awareness. Salience is defined as whether or not a case is on the list of cases reported in <i>Congressional Quarterly’s Guide to the U.S. Supreme Court</i> (from now on called the “CQ” measure). That is, a list created by authorities on the Supreme Court, updated after every term, based on their evaluation of what is now considered a landmark case. If a case appeared on CQ’s list of landmark Supreme Court cases, it was coded as “1;” consequently, if it did not, it was coded as a “o.”
Ideology (Party)	To control for ideology, Justices were coded manually based on the party of their appointing president with “1” denoting Republican and “o” denoting a Democratic appointee
Ideology (Ideal-Point)	As an added control for ideology, I have included the Bridge Ideal-Point model created by Dr. Michael Bailey. The ideal-point model operates on the premise that Justices can be placed on an ideological spectrum, typically ranging from liberal to conservative. Unlike more straightforward methods that classify Justices based solely on the president’s political party who appointed them or their votes in high-profile cases, Bailey’s model employs a multifaceted statistical approach to gauge ideology. In this study, Dr. Bailey’s ideal points for each Justice across each term were pulled and averaged to generate an ideological ideal-point score. For the purposes of this model, the greater the negative number, the more “liberal” a Justice is, and vice versa for more “conservative” ideological scores.